

THE DETERMINANTS OF HDI: HOW TO IMPROVE NATIONAL WELFARE?

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Abstract. This paper aims to identify effective strategies for improving the Human Development Index (HDI) in Uzbekistan. For this purpose, this paper analyzed 33 countries that made considerable progress in improving their HDI, increasing it from 0.7 to more than 0.8 points. Results suggest that economic growth, increasing educational attainment, and reducing population can improve HDI. The second part of the paper analyzes Central Asian countries and provides a graphical analysis of Uzbekistan. This analysis suggests that investing in healthcare and higher education can potentially improve people's welfare.

Keywords: HDI, schooling, sanitation, health

Аннотация. Целью данной статьи является выявление эффективных стратегий для улучшения Индекса Человеческого Развития (ИЧР) в Узбекистане. Для этого были проанализированы 33 стран, с значительным прогрессом в улучшение благосостояния народа, которые смогли увеличить ИЧР с 0,7 до более чем 0,8 единиц. Результаты показывают, что экономический рост, повышение уровня образования и сокращение численности населения способствовали улучшению ИЧР среди этих стран. Во второй части статьи представлен анализ для стран Центральной Азии и графический анализ Узбекистана. Вторая часть поднимает вопросы о важности инвестиций в сферу здравоохранения и высшего образования для улучшения качества жизни людей.

Ключевые слова: Индекса Человеческого Развития (ИЧР), повышение уровня образования, улучшение санитарии и здравоохранения

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola O'zbekistonda Inson taraqqiyoti indeksini (ITI) yaxshilash bo'yicha samarali strategiyalarni aniqlashga qaratilgan. Shu maqsadda ushbu maqolada inson taraqqiyoti indeksini 0,7 dan 0,8 ballgacha oshirishda sezilarli yutuqlarga erishgan 33 mamlakat tahlil qilindi. Analizning natijalariga ko'ra, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, ta'lim darajasini oshirish va aholining qisqarishi ushbu mamlakatlarda Inson taraqqiyoti indeksining yaxshilanishiga hissa qo'shgan. Maqolaning ikkinchi qismida Markaziy Osiyo mamlakatlari tahlil qilinib, O'zbekistonning grafik tahlili keltirilgan. Ikkinchi bo'limda odamlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilash uchun sog'liqni saqlash va oliy ta'limga sarmoya kiritish muhimligi muhokama qilinadi.

Tayanch tushunchalar: Inson taraqqiyoti indeksini (ITI), ta'lim darajasini oshirish, sanitariya va sog'liqni saqlashni yaxshilash

Introduction

Development goes beyond economic growth, income level, or production. It is people who matter (Haq, no date). Therefore, measuring human development through the means of GDP per capita is an inadequate representation of people's well-being (Akay and Van, 2017). In an attempt to create more representative indexes, UNDP introduced the Human Development Index (HDI) in 1990. Almost two decades later, the Oxford Poverty & Human Development Initiative (OPHI) introduced the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). Both HDI and MPI measure human well-being through three dimensions: health, education, and standards of living. When choosing between the two indexes, MPI provides a better picture, as it collects microdata at the household level. However, the data collection for MPI is often more expensive and time-consuming than HDI. Furthermore, MPI is not always reported on an annual basis, which does not allow one to

track changes continuously. Therefore, HDI can provide a good approximation of human development on an annual basis. Besides, Beja (2021) showed that both MPI and HDI provide equivalent information on human development.

For Uzbekistan, MPI is quite low (0.006), indicating a low level of multidimensional poverty. Similarly, in terms of HDI, Uzbekistan is ranked 101 in the “High Human Development” category as of 2021. Uzbekistan made enormous progress by improving HDI from 0.673 to 0.727 from 2010 to 2021, moving from medium to high development. However, in a slightly more than 10-year period, the position has changed from 102 to 101 in the global ranking. Among Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan is the third in its development (see Tables 1 and 2). Although it is a good indicator that Uzbekistan managed to preserve its position, unlike other central Asian countries (except Kazakhstan), Uzbekistan is developing a policy aimed at improving its ranking in HDI.

Table 1. HDI with its components for Central Asian countries, 2010

Country, as of 2010	Rank	HDI	Life Expectancy at Birth	Expected Years of Schooling	Mean Years of Schooling	GNI Per Capita
Kazakhstan	66	0.767	68	15	11	17976
Turkmenistan	87	0.711	68	11	11	12185
Uzbekistan	102	0.673	69	11	11	4943
Kyrgyzstan	109	0.664	68	12	11	3890
Tajikistan	112	0.636	68	11	11	2962

Table 2. HDI with its components for Central Asian countries, 2021

Country, as of 2021	Rank	HDI	Life Expectancy at Birth	Expected Years of Schooling	Mean Years of Schooling	GNI Per Capita
Kazakhstan	56	0.811	69	16	12	23943
Turkmenistan	91	0.745	69	13	11	13021
Uzbekistan	101	0.727	71	12	12	7917
Kyrgyzstan	118	0.692	70	13	11	4566
Tajikistan	122	0.685	72	12	11	4548

The policy aims to develop a strategy that improves the position of the country in the international rankings and indexes, including ranking in HDI. To increase the rank in HDI, it is essential to improve HDI and the improvement should be larger than in other countries. Against this background, this paper aims to provide possible strategies to improve HDI in Uzbekistan by analyzing international experience and identifying what influenced most the change in HDI of Uzbekistan and Central Asia.

What influences HDI? Findings of previous studies.

HDI has three components and improvement in one of these components can increase HDI. Despite the criticism, GDP per capita still plays an important role in increasing HDI by improving standards of living (Eren et al., 2014; Akay and Van, 2017; Arisman, 2018; Sangaji, 2016; Handalani, 2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019). Higher GDP per capita will increase the purchasing power of consumers and improve their living conditions. For this reason, many countries improved their HDI after experiencing rapid economic growth. On the other hand, inflation reduces the purchasing power of people and can negatively affect HDI (Arisman, 2018).

Similarly, a lack of employment opportunities can cause poverty and limit access to education and healthcare services by cutting the income flows of breadwinners (Eren et al., 2014). Except for economic determinants, some studies suggest that population growth can worsen HDI (Sangaji, 2016; Arisman, 2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019). At the household level, having more children is associated with reduced consumption per head. Similarly, at the national level, resources are limited, and consumption decreases if population growth outpaces economic growth. Finally, improvements in expected years of schooling and life expectancy at birth are required to increase HDI, as they are major components of the index (Eren et al., 2014; Sangaji, 2016; Akay and Van, 2017).

Some studies showed that increased private health expenditure can foster a healthy population and improve HDI (Akay and Van, 2017). However, increased private household spending on healthcare could indicate the presence of health problems. Positive relationships might be blurred by the fact that healthcare is expensive in developed countries, where HDI is high, and vice versa. And only for this reason, higher spending is correlated with higher HDI. Therefore, it is important to understand the effect of healthcare investment on people's welfare. Several studies tried to measure investment through FDI or foreign aid. Both FDI and Foreign aid are proven to be effective in uplifting the wellbeing of the nation. Foreign aid on health provided by developed countries to developing nations can reduce infant mortality (Mishra and Newhouse, 2009; Feeny and Ouattara, 2013; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019). However, unlike foreign aid that is provided for nations with extreme issues, FDI can be attracted to any other sector irrespective of the severity of the problem. Handalani (2018) suggested that it is important to foster a favorable environment for investments to attract FDI. The flow of FDI can stimulate job creation and thus in the long run increase public consumption, improving human welfare.

The rest of the paper is divided into three parts. First, this paper describes the methods implemented in the study and identifies countries that successfully improved their HDI. These countries are analyzed by regression analysis using the determinants discussed above. This section also determines the main components of the HDI that lead to the growth of these countries. The second section also includes regression for Central Asian countries. Finally, this paper presents a graphical analysis of Uzbekistan and suggests possible policy recommendations.

1) How other countries improved their ranking?

Methods

As this paper aims to identify effective strategies to increase HDI, an analysis of international experience is provided first. The data is collected from UNDP Human Development reports from 1990 to 2020. First, this paper identifies countries with considerable growth in HDI. To accomplish this task, countries with HDI similar to the current HDI of Uzbekistan were selected. In other words, as Uzbekistan's HDI was 0.727 in 2021, countries whose HDI in 1990 was 0.75 or lower, were selected for the analysis. Then the list was further reduced by keeping those countries whose HDI increased to 0.8 or more by 2021. The list of countries is provided in Appendix A Table A1. The second step is to conduct a regression analysis. As the data is of panel structure, this study used fixed and random effects. Diagnostic Test showed that data suffers from heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, and for this reason, standard errors are adjusted using Driscoll Kraay's adjustment (see Appendix B). According to the Hausman test, fixed effect is more appropriate for the analysis.

The independent variables include the fertility rate to account for population growth. It was previously shown that increasing population negatively affects HDI (Sangaji, 2016; Arisman,

2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019). The model also tests the effect of economic change on the HDI, using the unemployment rate, inflation (GDP deflator), and GDP per capita (\$PPP). As education is often believed to improve welfare (Eren et al., 2014; Akay and Van, 2017), the average educational attainment for the population aged 15 is included in the model. Finally, this study also controls FDI to identify the effect of foreign investment in improving consumption and job opportunities locally. Table 3 presents summary statistics for the countries with considerable progress in HDI.

Table 3. Summary Statistics for International countries

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Obs.
HDI	0.79	0.07	0.48	0.95	1090
Fertility Rate	1.91	0.74	0.84	6.61	1078
Inflation (GDP deflator)	39.42	517.10	-27.63	15444.38	1084
Unemployment	7.17	4.61	0.25	24.40	1085
ln(GDP per capita, PPP)	9.83	0.80	6.89	11.67	1094
Average Educational Attainment (15+)	7.89	2.18	2.06	12.40	1023
FDI	8.12	28.68	-117.42	449.08	1072
<i>N</i>	1120				

Table 3 shows that the average HDI is 0.79 for these countries across all years. On average, there are two children per married woman, with some families having up to 6 children, who can obtain eight years of education. Regarding economic metrics, 7% of the workforce is unemployed, with GDP per capita accounting for 18.5 thousand international dollars per person. On average, 40% of GDP can be attributed to inflation, three times higher than that of Uzbekistan. FDI accounts for 8% of GDP, with a high deviation of 28.6%. For this reason, some countries received FDI as high as 449% of their GDP.

HDI Components

Decomposed HDI for these countries is provided in Appendix A, Table A2 and A3. Table A2 on contributions shows that these countries achieved increased HDI by increasing the average years of schooling. The index for schooling was as low as 0.48 and increased to 0.76. This accounts for an increase in the mean years of schooling from 7 to 11 years (see Table A3). However, in the case of Uzbekistan, average schooling is already high throughout the period. As of 2021, Uzbekistan has 12 years of schooling for almost all children.

Unlike Uzbekistan, these countries also improved the expected years of education, which includes bachelor's and master's degrees. As a result, they were able to increase the expected years of schooling for children who just started their educational journey from 11 years to 16 years, meaning that, on average, children are expected to earn a bachelor's degree. In contrast, both expected and average schooling are the same in Uzbekistan. This comparison shows that Uzbekistan needs to invest in higher education to increase further the HDI. Furthermore, most of these countries (China, Ireland, South Korea, Poland, Singapore, and Thailand) experienced rapid economic growth during the period, which enhanced standards of living for their population. Economic growth is key to creating job opportunities, increasing production, and encouraging consumption, which will improve the HDI and welfare of people. Currently, the life expectancy of people in Uzbekistan is 71 years old, which is equivalent to the average age for our listed countries in 1990. Therefore, it is important to aim to increase the life expectancy of the Uzbek population by targeting 77 or 78 years of age. It is possible to achieve this by investing in the healthcare system and improving the lifestyle of the population.

Regression Analysis

Table 5 shows the regression analysis for international countries. The Random effects model explains 82% of the variation in HDI, whereas Fixed Effects explains 93%. However, the R squared is high due to the high correlation of variables and autocorrelation.

Findings suggest that the fertility rate decreases HDI. A larger population often implies the need for larger investments and more resources. There is a higher probability that food production will not be sufficient to feed the whole population, and schools will be overcrowded, decreasing the quality of teaching. Therefore, several countries encourage birth control to reduce population growth (Eren et al., 2014; Sangaji, 2016; Arisman, 2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019). China is one of the examples that adopted a one-child policy to reduce its population. Therefore, economic growth and lower population growth contributed to the improved HDI. The development of the country also positively influences HDI. An increase in GDP per capita positively influences the level of development for the selected countries, statistically significant across both models. This study failed to establish a strong connection between unemployment, inflation, and HDI. The results are insignificant for both models. Similarly, FDI has almost no effect on HDI. However, increasing years of education considerably improves the index ceteris paribus (Eren et al., 2014; Akay and Van, 2017). People with higher education often work in less hazardous jobs and earn larger salaries. This affects both their health and consumption. It is believed that high-skilled workers are often those who completed tertiary education. Therefore, the larger educated population can contribute to the economic development of the country and uplift the well-being of the nation.

Table 4. International experience: Regression analysis for countries with high HDI growth

	Fixed Effects		Random Effects	
	Estimate	Drisc/Kraay Std. Error	Estimate	Drisc/Kraay Std. Error
Fertility Rate	-0.0223***	(0.0017)	-0.0248***	(0.0039)
Inflation (GDP deflator)	0.0000	(0.0000)	0.0000	(0.0000)
Unemployment	-0.0002	(0.0002)	-0.0002	(0.0002)
ln(GDP per capita, PPP)	0.0590***	(0.0078)	0.0641***	(0.0056)
Average Educational Attainment (15+)	0.0233***	(0.0034)	0.0200***	(0.0024)
FDI	0.0000	(0.0000)	0.0000	(0.0000)
_cons	0.0640	(0.0531)	0.0440	(0.0462)
R^2	0.9302		0.8188	
Wald chi2			13059.00	
F	1143.9037			
N	929		929	

Standard errors in parentheses
* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

2) HDI in Central Asia

Methods

Finally, this paper provides regression analysis for Central Asian countries to test which aspects should be improved to increase HDI. The data covers period from 2000 to 2019. This study incorporates fixed effect and random effect models. According to Hausman test fixed effect model is more adequate measure for our analysis, yet this paper present both fixed and random effect models for comparison. As the data suffers from autocorrelation Driscoll Kraay adjustment is used. Due to the limited number of years and consideration of only 5 countries, number of variables cannot be more than four. Therefore, this paper considered two variables for social development and two variables for economic development. Social variables include average years of schooling to account for education and number of deaths caused because of using unsafe sanitation facilities to account for health. The later variable is in log form to minimize the variation. This study considers death due to unimproved sanitation because when constructing MPI, the largest population is deprived in sanitation. Therefore, the deaths due to unimproved sanitation is included as a variable that can potentially worsen HDI and shorten expected lifespan of people. Regarding, economic variables, job creation is often followed by higher economic growth and thus, the study controlled for employment. Finally, positive FDI can boost economy, just like in the case of South Korea and Singapore. Table 4 presents summary statistics for Central Asia and table A6 in Appendix A provides detailed information on variable definitions and data sources.

Table 5. Summary Statistics for Central Asia

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Obs.
HDI (x100)	69.09	5.85	56.00	81.90	105
Employment	60.59	11.53	41.90	78.03	110
Average Educational Attainment	8.80	0.73	7.03	10.12	90
FDI	5.01	4.33	-5.16	22.52	109
Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)	5.03	1.03	3.19	7.47	100
<i>N</i>	110				

It is clear from the table 4 that central Asian countries receive on average 5% FDI., with 60.59 of its labor force being occupied in formal sector. Across the study period average years of education is equal to 8 years. Regarding health indicators, there are on average, 153 deaths due to unimproved sanitation, while approximately 52% population has problems with sanitation (see Table A5, Appendix A).

Results

Table 6 provides regression results for Central Asian countries. Only three variables (including constant term) are significant, and the model explains 77% of the variation in HDI in the case of random effects and 96% in the case of Fixed Effects. The positive coefficient in employment suggests that an increase in employment can increase HDI. However, it is statistically insignificant. This can be explained by the fact that some portion of the population finds employment in the informal sector, and therefore, there is a weak relationship. Furthermore, Uzbek people tend to work for longer hours or work during the weekends. The lack of leisure time can reduce the productivity of workers and negatively affect their health conditions. Therefore, employment has a weak relationship, because, even though employment ensures the constant flow of income and increases consumption, it could also indicate poor health due to excessive working hours. FDI has insignificant results as well. The effect of FDI might be unnoticed as the benefits

of investment are often seen in the long term. Incorporating lags could identify a positive relationship. However, this study did not use lags due to the already low number of observations.

One year increase in average educational attainment increases HDI by 1.97 (0.0197) points. The results are highly significant in both models. As education is one of the components of HDI, improving education and making it accessible for all layers of the population increases HDI. Furthermore, deaths due to unsafe sanitation have a negative impact on HDI, meaning that it can decrease HDI by 4 (0.04) points. Although this data considers Central Asia, it can be seen that problems with sanitation considerably decrease the living standard of people and can even result in death. Solving this problem can considerably improve HDI.

Table 6. Regression analysis for Central Asia

	Random Effects		Fixed Effects	
	Estimate	Drisc/Kraay Std. Error	Estimate	Drisc/Kraay Std. Error
Employment	0.0246	(0.0144)	0.0322	(0.0730)
Average Educational Attainment	0.6824***	(0.0946)	1.9771***	(0.2087)
FDI	0.1717	(0.1007)	0.0255	(0.0242)
In Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)	-4.3103***	(0.1718)	-4.3646***	(0.2074)
_cons	81.5540***	(1.5696)	70.2196***	(6.5221)
R^2	0.7724		0.9609	
Wald chi2	6832.12***			
F			1637.2177***	
N	95		95	

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Given the above findings, the following policy recommendations can be drawn. It is important to invest in higher education. In recent years, Uzbekistan has already encouraged education in higher education institutions by providing scholarships for studying abroad (e.g. El-Yurt Umidi scholarship) and covering tuition fees for females pursuing master's. For these scholarships to be effective, students receiving scholarships for studying abroad should return to Uzbekistan and contribute to the development of the country. The scholarship can include terms for those who studied abroad to teach in local universities. This approach will bring new knowledge into the country, obtained from foreign nations. Furthermore, several foreign universities have opened their subsidiaries on the premises of Uzbekistan, blending international experience with the Uzbek educational system. By learning from developed countries, it is possible to contribute to the development of science and thus generate new knowledge locally. Finally, there is a need to invest in the development of local universities and increase the quality of education. As the majority of universities are concentrated in Tashkent, it is also recommended to increase the number of educational institutions in other regions. By increasing the quality of education and the number of students, completing university can considerably improve HDI.

The graph below shows the government expenditure on education as percentage of total public spending and HDI. Although in earlier years, government spending was reducing and HDI increasing, starting from 2018, the pattern of spending and HDI are similar. A decrease in the spending on education is followed by smaller increases in HDI, whereas an increase in spending is associated with larger growth in HDI. Although COVID negatively affected both HDI and reduced spending on education, HDI recovered by 2021.

Furthermore, despite the low MPI, it was found that the problem with sanitation is a major contributor to poverty. Therefore, the death resulting from poor sanitation could considerably decrease HDI.

Figure 3 shows that improving sanitation in rural areas and HDI follow the same increasing pattern. The yellow line shows the percentage of people with basic sanitation facilities as a share of the population. It shows the progress that Uzbekistan achieved in improving sanitation facilities. Although it is hard to conclude that HDI increased due to improved facilities, the graph depicts similar growth patterns.

It is recommended to initiate the project on the reconstruction of sanitation facilities in the household. The government could allocate resources for this project from social protection funds. It is possible to identify households in poverty using a Single Registry and initiate planned

reconstruction. In recent years, a considerable portion of investments has been directed to the construction industry. Therefore, these construction companies could be employed to improve sanitation facilities across Uzbekistan. Furthermore, this variable was a proxy for health welfare, meaning that to improve HDI it is important to invest in the healthcare sector. By improving the quality of healthcare services, it is possible to improve the well-being of the population. In conclusion, Uzbekistan can focus on 1) providing accessible and quality healthcare facilities to foster healthy population, 2) increasing the population with higher education, 3) reduce unemployment and provide stress free working environment with standard working hours.

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APPENDIX A.

Table A 1. List of countries with considerable increase in HDI

Country	1990	2021
United Arab Emirates	0.728	0.911
Argentina	0.723	0.842
Bahrain	0.742	0.875
Belarus	0.790*	0.808
Chile	0.706	0.855
China	0.484	0.768
Costa Rica	0.660	0.809
Cyprus	0.716	0.896

Czechia	0.742	0.889
Estonia	0.732	0.890
Georgia	0.759*	0.802
Hungary	0.720	0.846
Ireland	0.737	0.945
Kazakhstan	0.673	0.811
Korea (Republic of)	0.737	0.925
Kuwait	0.718	0.831
Lithuania	0.734	0.875
Latvia	0.730	0.863
Malta	0.730	0.918
Mauritius	0.626	0.802
Malaysia	0.640	0.803
Oman	0.788*	0.816
Panama	0.669	0.805
Poland	0.716	0.876
Portugal	0.701	0.866
Romania	0.703	0.821
Russian Federation	0.743	0.822
Saudi Arabia	0.678	0.875
Singapore	0.727	0.939
Serbia	0.767*	0.802
Slovakia	0.692	0.848
Thailand	0.576	0.800
Trinidad and Tobago	0.660	0.810
Türkiye	0.600	0.838
Uruguay	0.701	0.809
Uzbekistan	0.673*	0.727

* For countries that did not have information for the 1990s, the data for 2010 is taken and labeled with *.

Table A 2 Average HDI for 36 countries: Contributions

Year	HDI		Life Expectancy at Birth		Mean Years of Schooling		Expected Years of Schooling		GNI Per Capita	
	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB
1990	0.70		0.79	0.70	0.48		0.64	0.63	0.77	0.54
1991	0.70		0.79	0.69	0.49		0.64	0.62	0.76	0.53
1992	0.70		0.80	0.69	0.50		0.63	0.60	0.76	0.51
1993	0.71		0.80	0.69	0.51		0.64	0.60	0.76	0.50
1994	0.71		0.80	0.69	0.52		0.65	0.60	0.77	0.49
1995	0.72		0.80	0.69	0.54		0.66	0.60	0.77	0.49
1996	0.72		0.81	0.69	0.55		0.67	0.60	0.77	0.49
1997	0.73		0.81	0.69	0.56		0.69	0.60	0.78	0.49
1998	0.74		0.82	0.69	0.57		0.70	0.60	0.78	0.50
1999	0.75		0.82	0.70	0.58		0.72	0.59	0.78	0.50

2000	0.75	0.61	0.83	0.70	0.59	0.67	0.73	0.60	0.79	0.50
2001	0.76	0.61	0.83	0.71	0.60	0.68	0.74	0.61	0.79	0.51
2002	0.76	0.62	0.83	0.72	0.61	0.68	0.75	0.62	0.80	0.51
2003	0.77	0.63	0.84	0.72	0.62	0.69	0.77	0.63	0.80	0.52
2004	0.78	0.63	0.84	0.73	0.63	0.69	0.77	0.64	0.81	0.53
2005	0.79	0.64	0.84	0.73	0.64	0.70	0.78	0.64	0.82	0.53
2006	0.79	0.64	0.85	0.74	0.65	0.71	0.78	0.64	0.83	0.54
2007	0.80	0.66	0.85	0.74	0.66	0.71	0.79	0.64	0.84	0.56
2008	0.81	0.66	0.86	0.75	0.67	0.72	0.80	0.63	0.84	0.57
2009	0.81	0.67	0.86	0.75	0.67	0.73	0.81	0.63	0.83	0.58
2010	0.81	0.67	0.87	0.76	0.68	0.73	0.82	0.64	0.84	0.59
2011	0.82	0.68	0.87	0.76	0.69	0.74	0.82	0.64	0.84	0.60
2012	0.83	0.69	0.88	0.77	0.70	0.74	0.83	0.65	0.85	0.61
2013	0.83	0.69	0.88	0.77	0.70	0.75	0.84	0.65	0.85	0.62
2014	0.84	0.70	0.89	0.77	0.71	0.76	0.85	0.65	0.85	0.62
2015	0.84	0.70	0.89	0.78	0.72	0.76	0.86	0.65	0.86	0.63
2016	0.85	0.71	0.89	0.78	0.72	0.78	0.86	0.66	0.86	0.64
2017	0.85	0.72	0.89	0.78	0.73	0.78	0.87	0.67	0.86	0.64
2018	0.85	0.72	0.90	0.79	0.74	0.78	0.88	0.68	0.87	0.65
2019	0.86	0.73	0.90	0.79	0.75	0.79	0.88	0.69	0.87	0.65
2020	0.85	0.72	0.89	0.77	0.76	0.79	0.88	0.69	0.86	0.65
2021	0.85	0.73	0.88	0.78	0.76	0.79	0.88	0.69	0.87	0.66

Table A 3 Average HDI for 36 countries: by Components

Year	HDI		Life Expectancy at Birth		Mean Years of Schooling		Expected Years of Schooling		GNI Per Capita	
	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB	Mean	UZB
1990	0.695		71	65	7		11	11	20657	3473
1991	0.697		72	65	7		11	11	19919	3375
1992	0.700		72	65	8		11	11	20300	2928
1993	0.706		72	65	8		12	11	20915	2802
1994	0.712		72	65	8		12	11	21506	2601
1995	0.717		72	65	8		12	11	21941	2528
1996	0.725		73	65	8		12	11	22449	2517
1997	0.733		73	65	8		12	11	23227	2584
1998	0.740		73	65	9		13	11	23418	2667
1999	0.745		73	65	9		13	11	23317	2733
2000	0.751	0.607	74	66	9	10	13	11	24278	2741
2001	0.758	0.614	74	66	9	10	13	11	24407	2853
2002	0.765	0.621	74	67	9	10	14	11	24486	2944
2003	0.772	0.627	74	67	9	10	14	11	25488	3041
2004	0.779	0.634	75	67	9	10	14	11	26671	3251
2005	0.786	0.639	75	67	10	11	14	11	27674	3439
2006	0.792	0.644	75	68	10	11	14	11	28901	3568
2007	0.800	0.656	75	68	10	11	14	12	29765	4101

2008	0.806	0.659	76	69	10	11	14	11	29871	4241
2009	0.809	0.665	76	69	10	11	15	11	28205	4500
2010	0.815	0.673	76	69	10	11	15	11	28765	4943
2011	0.820	0.68	77	70	10	11	15	11	29468	5275
2012	0.825	0.687	77	70	10	11	15	12	30064	5600
2013	0.831	0.693	77	70	11	11	15	12	30783	5978
2014	0.837	0.698	78	70	11	11	15	12	31405	6259
2015	0.842	0.701	78	70	11	11	15	12	32306	6485
2016	0.846	0.709	78	71	11	12	16	12	32885	6726
2017	0.851	0.715	78	71	11	12	16	12	33677	6974
2018	0.855	0.72	78	71	11	12	16	12	34244	7303
2019	0.859	0.726	78	71	11	12	16	12	34789	7499
2020	0.853	0.721	78	70	11	12	16	12	32937	7512
2021	0.852	0.727	77	71	11	12	16	12	34794	7917

Table A 4 Variables Definition and Expected Sign

Variable	Measure	Expected sign	Data Source	Liturature
Fertility Rate for population growth	Total births per woman	-	World Bank, 2022	Eren, Celik, and Kubat, 2014; Sangaji, 2016; Arisman, 2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019;
Inflation	GDP deflator (annual %)	-	World Bank, 2022	Arisman, 2018; Sangaji, 2016; Handalani, 2018
Unemployment	Unemployment rate as % of labor force	-	World Bank, 2022	Eren, Celik, and Kubat, 2014; Arisman, 2018
GDP per capita as income per capita	Log of GDP per capita, PPP (current international \$)	+	World Bank, 2022	Eren, Celik, and Kubat, 2014; Akay and Van, 2017; Arisman, 2018; Sangaji, 2016; Handalani, 2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019;
Life expectancy at birth	Expected number of years a person will live starting from birth	+	World Bank, 2022	Eren, Celik, and Kubat, 2014; Sangaji, 2016;
Years of schooling	Average Years of Schooling for individuals over 15-year-old	+	Wittgenstein Centre Human Capital Data Explorer, 2020	Eren, Celik, and Kubat, 2014; Akay and Van, 2017

Expected years of schooling	Number of years of schooling that a child can expect to receive when starting a school		UNDP, 2021	
FDI	net inflows of FDI as % of GDP	+		Handalani, 2018; Toseef, Jensen, and Tarraf, 2019;

Table A 5. Uncensored Headcount Ratios: Percentage of the population deprived in each indicator: MPI

Deprivations	Mean	Linearized std. err.	[95% conf. interval]	
Assets	0.10077	0.00676	0.0875	0.11404
Water	0.03251	0.00478	0.02313	0.0419
School Attendance	0.00023	0.00017	-1E-04	0.00057
Electricity	0.00781	0.00184	0.00419	0.01143
Housing materials	0.00075	0.00037	1.4E-05	0.00148
Sanitation	0.54394	0.01413	0.51619	0.57169
Cooking fuel	0.2009	0.00988	0.18149	0.22031
Child Mortality	0.04581	0.00534	0.03532	0.0563
	0.01783	0.00261	0.0127	0.02295
Multidimensional Poverty Index		0.00610		

Table A 6 Variables for Central Asian regression model

Variable	Measure	Expected sign	Data Source
HDI (x100)	Human Development Index rescaled to 100		
Employment	Labor force participation rate, total (% of total population ages 15-64) (modeled ILO estimate)	+	World bank, 2022
Average Educational Attainment	Average Years of Schooling for individuals over 15 year old	+	Wittgenstein Centre Human Capital Data Explorer , 2020
FDI	Foreign direct investment are the net inflows of investment to acquire a lasting management interest (10 percent or more of voting stock) in an enterprise operating in an economy other than that of the investor. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, other long-term capital, and short-term capital as shown in the balance of payments. This series shows net inflows (new investment inflows less disinvestment) in the reporting economy from	+	World bank, 2022

foreign investors, and is divided by GDP.

Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)	Deaths that are from all causes attributed to unsafe sanitation, in both sexes aged all ages	-	Our World in Data, 2019
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APPENDIX B. Data Analysis

For countries with large HDI progress

Equation 1. Hausman Test

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

$\text{chi2}(6) = 35.04$

$\text{Prob} > \text{chi2} = 0.0000$

We reject H0 and conclude that fixed effects model is more appropriate than random effects.

Table 7. Correlation matrix.

	HDI	Fertility Rate	Inflation (GDP deflator)	Unemployment	ln(GDP per capita, PPP)	Average Educational Attainment (15+)	FDI
HDI	1.0						
Fertility Rate	-0.5	1.0					
Inflation (GDP deflator)	-0.2	0.1	1.0				
Unemployment	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	1.0			
ln(GDP per capita, PPP)	0.8	-0.2	-0.2	-0.4	1.0		
Average Educational Attainment (15+)	0.5	-0.5	-0.1	0.4	0.1	1.0	
FDI	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	1.0

The highest correlation is 50%. However, it is not perfect correlation and therefore variables were preserved

Equation 2 Test for Heteroscedasticity

H0: Constant variance

$\text{chi2}(1) = 11.16$

$\text{Prob} > \text{chi2} = 0.0008$

We reject H0 and conclude that data suffers for heteroscedasticity. Robust standard errors and Driscal Kray adjustment solves this problem.

Equation 3 Test for autocorrelation

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

$$F(1, 32) = 161.766$$

$$\text{Prob} > F = 0.0000$$

We reject H0 and conclude that there is autocorrelation. Driscoll-Kraay adjustment is used to address this problem.

For Central Asian countries

Equation 4 Hausman Test

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\chi^2(4) = 30.62$$

$$\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$$

We reject H0 and conclude that Fixed effects model is appropriate.

Equation 5 Test for Heteroscedasticity

Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

H0: Constant variance

$$\chi^2(1) = 0.99$$

$$\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.3195$$

We fail to reject H0 at 1% significance level and conclude that variances are constant.

Table 8 Correlation Matrix

	HDI	Employment	Education	FDI	Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)
HDI	1.00				
Employment	0.50	1.00			
Education	0.32	-0.01	1.00		
FDI	0.25	0.07	-0.27	1.00	
Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)	-0.87	-0.57	-0.29	-0.19	1.00

Correlation is high for number of deaths due to unimproved sanitation. However, this variable is believed to be important and thus kept despite the high correlation. It is still not considered to be perfect multicollinearity.

Table 9 Correlation matrix for desired variables

	HDI	Unemployment	ln(GDP per capita, PPP)	Education	FDI	Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)	Life Expectancy at Birth
HDI	1.00						
Unemployment	-0.73	1.00					
ln(GDP per capita, PPP)	0.97	-0.73	1.00				
Education	0.32	-0.58	0.37	1.00			
FDI	0.25	-0.08	0.27	-0.27	1.00		
Death due to unsafe sanitation (Log)	-0.87	0.80	-0.84	-0.29	-0.19	1.00	
Life Expectancy at Birth	0.57	-0.63	0.40	0.44	-0.17	-0.59	1.00

As Unemployment highly correlated with all variables, it was substituted with formal employment rate. GDP per capita was not included due to high correlation. And both GDP per capita and life expectancy were not included as they are components of HDI.

Equation 6 Omitted variables bias

Ramsey RESET test for omitted variables

Omitted: Powers of fitted values of HDI

H0: Model has no omitted variables

$F(3, 83) = 1.78$

$\text{Prob} > F = 0.1570$

Fail to reject Ho and conclude that there are no omitted variables. Due to low number of observations, extra control variable cannot be added to the model. The cluster includes only 5 countries, thus only 4 variables can be used to estimate F (Wald chi) statistics

Equation 7 Test for autocorrelation

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data

H0: no first-order autocorrelation

$F(1, 4) = 19.136$

$\text{Prob} > F = 0.0119$

We reject Ho at 5% significance level and conclude that data suffers from autocorrelation. Driscall Krays adjustment is used to address this problem.